

CORRELATION OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION MARKERS WITH RETINOPATHY SEVERITY IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Abstract: Endothelial dysfunction and hemostasis disorders in the cerebral vessels play a key role in the development of cerebrovascular lesions in patients with diabetes. The development and progression of microcirculation disorders and brain tissue ischemia are influenced by factors such as hyper- and hypoglycemia, hyperinsulinemia, insulin resistance, and overweight. Transcranial Doppler sonography is successfully used for non-invasive assessment of hemodynamic changes.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, cerebral angiopathy, endothelial dysfunction

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is the third leading cause of death after cardiovascular and oncological diseases. The main cause of disability and death in diabetes mellitus is micro- and macrovascular complications, which lead to the development of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases. Diabetes mellitus increases the risk of myocardial infarction and ischemic stroke and leads to worse outcomes [1-4]. Cerebral microangiopathy is part of the common vascular complications observed in diabetes mellitus, and the frequent adverse consequences in these patients may be associated with the systemic nature of the vascular lesion and the negative effect of hyperglycemia on the ischemic process [2, 4].

In the development of cerebral angiopathy, a significant role is played by the violation of local hemostasis in the vessels of the brain. Normally, the fluid state of the blood is maintained due to the dynamic balance of platelet and plasma connections of hemostasis and the athrombogenicity of the vascular wall. Violation of at least one of these components leads to the activation of thrombus formation. In diabetes mellitus, damage to the inner layer of the vascular wall - the endothelium - is observed first of all [5]. It is the endothelium that plays a key role in maintaining vascular tone (vasodilation and vasoconstriction) and hemostasis (synthesis and inhibition of fibrinolysis factors and platelet aggregation); in the development of remodeling (synthesis and inhibition of proliferation factors) and local inflammation (production of pro- and anti-inflammatory factors) [6, 7]. The endothelium normally provides trophic and protective functions in relation to other layers of the vascular wall.

Research methods and materials: The location of the endothelium adjacent to the blood flow makes it vulnerable to the influence of various risk factors for the development of vascular complications, including hyperglycemia [2-4]. Endothelial dysfunction is accompanied by impaired blood coagulation, decreased fibrinolysis, increased fibrinogen levels, decreased expression of tissue plasminogen activator (t-PA),

decreased activity of plasminogen activator type 1 inhibitor (PAI-1), von Willebrand factor, factor VII and anticoagulants, anticoagulants (III protein). A number of studies have identified an association with the development of thrombotic vascular complications in diabetes mellitus [8].

The earliest events occurring in the endothelium of the vascular wall are the interaction of polymorphonuclear leukocytes, monocytes, and macrophages with the damaged endothelial layer, leading to its activation. This process is accompanied by a significant increase in the synthesis of platelet-activating factor (PAF) by endothelial cells and the formation of adhesion proteins. Monocytes and macrophages involved in adhesion processes are subsequently able to synthesize and secrete chemokines, cytokines, and mitogens, in particular, platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF). These, in turn, lead to the activation of the migration and growth of smooth muscle cells and fibroblasts, the maintenance of chronic inflammation in the muscular wall of the vessel, and the development of atherosclerotic lesions [9]. Dysfunction of the vascular endothelium is accompanied by changes in the content of endothelins, von Willebrand factor, tissue plasminogen activator, and nitric oxide (NO). Along with the decrease in vasodilators, there is a significant increase in the level of vasoconstrictors and procoagulants [10], which leads to deterioration of microcirculation, ischemia of surrounding tissues and their progressive damage under conditions of prolonged ischemia-hypoxia. Endothelial NO is involved in platelet aggregation [11] and leukocyte adhesion [12] and plays an important role in the autoregulation of cerebral blood flow.

Results: Autoregulation of cerebral blood flow is characterized by the ability of cerebral vessels to maintain a relatively constant volumetric rate of cerebral blood flow when the difference between systemic arterial and intracranial pressure varies over a wide range (from 80 to 180 mm Hg in normotensive individuals). This maintains the stability of cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP). The chemoregulation process consists in the ability of cerebral arterioles to respond to changes in the concentration of CO₂ in the blood. In response to a decrease in CO₂, the vessels constrict, and in response to an increase in CO₂ concentration, on the contrary, they dilate; such reactions are due to the ability of the endothelium to release NO under hypoxic conditions, which initiates relaxation [14] and is the basis of endothelium-dependent vasodilation (EDV).

In diabetes, endothelial function is impaired and local NO production is reduced. Constant exposure to risk factors contributes to the development of endothelial dysfunction, changes in the structure of the vascular wall, which is of great importance for the development of cerebral angiopathy in patients with diabetes.

Histological studies of the brain in people with diabetes reveal pathological changes at the level of the cerebral microcirculatory system: microatheromas, lipid and hyaline deposits, thickening of the basement membrane [15]. Histopathological changes are observed mainly in vessels with a diameter of 40-200 μm and in arterioles with a diameter of 300-500 μm [16]. Vessels with a diameter of more than 200 μm are responsible for the vasomotor reactions of the brain, and their damage is explained by a decrease in the reactivity of cerebral arteries to external stimuli.

Macroangiopathic changes can be detected by transcranial Doppler ultrasound (TCD) of the carotid and vertebral arteries. TCD allows for the assessment of cerebral perfusion reserve (CPR) and also allows for the noninvasive assessment of hemodynamic changes, in particular vasodilation induced by various stimuli [17]. Various pharmacological agents can be used for this purpose, including acetazolamide (Diacarb), a reversible inhibitor of the extracellular acidosis-causing enzyme carbonic anhydrase, which is a potent stimulator of arteriolar dilation when administered intravenously [18]. Vasodilation leads to a decrease in cerebrovascular resistance (CVR) and, consequently, an increase in cerebral blood flow, which can be determined by measuring blood flow velocity in the middle cerebral artery (MCA). Vasomotor reactivity of the brain is one of the main mechanisms of cerebral blood flow autoregulation. Studies have shown that patients with long-term diabetes have impaired cerebrovascular reserve (CVR) and reserve capacity

compared with non-diabetic individuals [19]. Impaired CVR is associated with systemic damage to cerebral arterioles and may result in a less intense vasodilatory response to acetazolamide administration.

Discussion: The dynamic effect of NO on the regulation of cerebral blood flow has been demonstrated by the ability of NG-monomethyl-L-arginine (L-NMMA, a nonselective inhibitor of NO synthase) to reduce basal cerebral blood flow [20]. In response to L-NMMA administration, a rapid and dose-dependent decrease in blood flow velocity occurs in the middle carotid artery. The lack of a decrease in blood flow velocity in the MCA suggests that L-NMMA causes vasoconstriction [21]. Nazir FS et al. [22] showed that basal NO activity is reduced in cerebral arteries in patients with type 2 diabetes (T2DM). This may indicate a decrease in NO production or a decrease in basal sensitivity in these vessels. As a result, the vasoconstrictor effect of L-NMMA on cerebral arteries is attenuated. No correlation was found between blood glucose levels and the SMA response to L-NMMA administration [22], which supports the multifactorial etiology of vascular dysfunction.

Determination of CVR and CVS allows us to get an idea of the changes in the function of cerebral arterioles, which are associated with impaired autoregulation of cerebral blood flow, which may be associated with microangiopathic changes. The results of a number of studies [19, 23] showed that in patients with a disease duration of more than 10 years, a decrease in the vasodilator response is observed. In addition, a negative linear correlation was established between the duration of the disease, CVS and CPR [24].

Currently, the effects of factors such as insulin, glucose, blood pressure (BP), etc. on endothelial function have been demonstrated.

Hyperglycemia plays an important role in the development of micro- and macrovascular cerebrovascular pathology. The consequences of chronic hyperglycemia are the following hemodynamic disorders: dilation and hyperperfusion of cerebral microvessels, increased intracapillary hydrostatic pressure, impaired autoregulation of capillary blood flow, i.e. the ability to maintain a stable blood flow when hydraulic pressure increases. Vasodilation and hyperperfusion of brain tissue are accompanied by an increase in intracapillary pressure, which affects the vascular endothelium and basement membrane. It is believed that high plasma glucose concentrations block vascular adrenergic receptors, resulting in a loss of their ability to contract in response to catecholamines and other vasoconstrictors. The response to increased hydraulic pressure is the active synthesis of vascular relaxation factors (prostacyclin, endothelial relaxing factor) by endothelial cells [1], as well as increased production of collagen, fibronectin, procoagulant proteins and von Willebrand factor; there is a violation of fibrinolytic potential, proliferation and migration [25]. Endothelial damage leads to stimulation of the synthesis of growth factors, cytokines and vasoactive substances by other cells [26]. Park JV et al. [27] found that patients with diabetes mellitus have increased production of endothelin-1, a potent vasoconstrictor, the content of which increases under hyperglycemia. It has been shown that the acceleration of blood flow observed during the manifestation of T1DM is associated with increased release of NO in response to hyperglycemia [26]. However, prolonged hyperglycemia, which stimulates the polyol pathway of glucose metabolism, leads to a decrease in glutathione and NADPH in endothelial cells. In addition, hyperglycemia increases the activity of diacylglycerol and protein kinase C, which also reduces NO formation by inhibiting endothelial NO synthase. Chronic hyperglycemia contributes to an increase in the amount of glycated hemoglobin and other advanced glycation end products [25] and is known to be one of the most important factors in the pathogenesis of vascular complications of diabetes. Advanced glycation end products reduce the availability or “quench” the activity of nitric oxide and are another additional factor in endothelial dysfunction. Chronic hyperglycemia leads to glycosylation of many proteins and substrates in the body, including LDL, which becomes more sensitive to the effects of free radicals generated by oxidative stress observed in diabetes. In severe hyperglycemia, an increase in cerebral blood flow is observed in the setting

of hyperglycemic ketoacidosis [28]. Excess glucose can have a toxic effect on neurons due to an increase in glycolysis products, activation of lipid peroxidation and apoptosis [11]. Thus, hyperglycemia, as a factor that disrupts endothelial function, can lead to a decrease in vascular reactivity and, as a result, to a disruption of the central venous system. Previous observations have shown that in patients with diabetes, unlike healthy people, cerebral blood flow is often unstable and reduced, but this is not associated with the level of blood glucose [29] and insulin [30] at the time of the study. Data from other experimental and clinical studies indicate a decrease in cerebral blood flow and dilation of cerebral vessels in response to hyperglycemia [21, 31]. Some authors describe increased cerebral blood flow in diabetic patients with poor glycemic control [32, 33].

In a study of patients aged 12 to 21 years, hyperglycemia, disease duration, or total cholesterol levels did not affect CVR indices [34]. Patients with blood glucose levels above 300 mg/dL showed a decrease in vascular reactivity to an increase in PCO₂. These results suggest that the stiffness of the CMA wall is increased in the early stages of the disease and may be an early indicator of endothelial dysfunction.

In patients with diabetes, episodes of hypoglycemia may occur alongside hyperglycemia. Hypoglycemia induced by hyperinsulinemia may lead to increased cerebral blood flow [5], which is considered a protective mechanism, but this effect is not observed in normoglycemic hyperinsulinemia [6]. Hypoglycemia has been shown to be detrimental to the brain [7], and there is evidence that severe and/or prolonged hypoglycemia is associated with neurological damage [8].

Insulin in peripheral blood plays a key role in maintaining vascular tone and endothelial function by affecting the background (basal) level of endothelial NO [39]. Insulin exerts a protective effect on blood vessels by activating phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase in endothelial cells and microvessels, which leads to the expression of the endothelial NO synthase gene and endothelial cell and vasodilation. However, insulin deficiency and hyperglycemia are known to be factors that increase NO production by macrophages in streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice [4]. Increased NO synthesis by monocytes may be a compensatory physiological effect, since macrophages engage in cellular cooperation to synthesize it, and it seems that the contribution of monocytes to the total production of NO is important for the regulation of vascular tone.

Previous studies have shown that elevated glucose and insulin levels can induce postprandial hypotension by stimulating baroreceptor reflexes, reducing cardiac output, and consequently reducing cerebral perfusion [2, 4]. This may explain the observation that some ischemic strokes occur after meals [4]. Theoretically, the increased cerebral perfusion resulting from the increase in blood glucose and insulin after meals should lead to activation of cerebral autoregulatory mechanisms and dilation of arterioles [43]. Since the acetazolamide test measures the true state of arteriolar resistance (the ability to dilate or constrict), heart rate should decrease after meals. However, a study involving patients with type 1 diabetes (T1DM) showed that CPR at different time points after meals was independent of true glucose and insulin levels [30]. An inverse correlation has been found between the ability of cerebral vessels to vasodilate and the duration of diabetes [4].

Insulin resistance leads to a decrease in insulin-stimulated NO production by endothelial and smooth muscle cells [3, 4]. It is known that excess insulin can also have a detrimental effect on the vascular wall by stimulating various growth factors through mitogen-activated protein kinase, which leads to the proliferation and migration of smooth muscle cells, their production of plasminogen activator-1 and the intensification of vascular remodeling and atherosclerosis [3, 7]. Currently, the fact of a close connection between insulin resistance and endothelial dysfunction, including NO synthesis, has been established, however, it is not possible to fully elucidate the cause-effect relationship between these processes.

Conclusion: Persistent arterial hypertension (AH) independently causes endothelial damage by increasing the level of adhesion molecules [4] and reducing the availability of NO [48]. There are different points of view on the question of the priority of endothelial dysfunction in hypertension. According to some authors, the endothelial dysfunction observed in hypertension is more a consequence of the disease than its cause, and represents premature aging of blood vessels as a result of chronic exposure to high blood pressure [9, 5]. According to other researchers, changes in EDVD in hypertension are a fundamental phenomenon, since its disorders can be observed in children and grandchildren of patients with essential hypertension, in addition, there is no clear relationship between EDVD and blood pressure, and EDVD does not normalize with a decrease in blood pressure [1, 2]. It is likely that hypertension and endothelial dysfunction form a “vicious circle” that promotes progression and mutual reinforcement. Endothelial dysfunction has been shown to be present in children and young adults with short-term type 1 diabetes [3] and may be a pathophysiological precursor of early atherosclerosis [4]. There is also evidence that changes in EDVD precede the increase in the intima-media complex (IMC) thickness of the common carotid arteries, which is observed with prolonged diabetes [5]. In patients with type 1 diabetes, a decrease in peak EDVT and an increase in IMC thickness are observed during the first decade of the disease compared with non-diabetic individuals [6]. Peppas-Patrikiou M. et al. [7] showed that atherosclerotic changes in the carotid arteries of adolescents and young adults with type 1 diabetes can be detected as early as three years after diagnosis. Jarvisalo JM et al. [8] noted similar changes in a younger age group.

List of used literature:

1. Долиев, М. Н. Тулакова, Г. Э. Кадырова, А. М. Юсупов, З. А., & Жалалова, Д. З. (2016). Эффективность комбинированного лечения пациентов с центральной серозной хориоретинопатией. Вестник Башкирского государственного медицинского университета, (2), 64-66.
2. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 282-288.
3. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 29-35.
4. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 545-550.
5. Begbudiyev M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 551-557.
6. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 558-563.
7. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 36-41.
8. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 409-414.
9. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 898-903.
10. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 413-419.

11. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 240-244.
12. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 385-391.
13. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 245-251.
14. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 230-235.
15. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 258-264.
16. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 392-397.
17. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 186-191.
18. Sedenkov V. et al. Clinical and socio-demographic characteristics of elderly patients with suicide attempts //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 273-277.
19. Sedenkov V. et al. Modern methods of diagnosing depressive disorders in neurotic and affective disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 361-366.
20. Zukhridinovna, Z. D. (2022). Modern aspects of neuroprotective treatment in hypertensive retinopathy.
21. Jalalova, D., Raxmonov, X., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). THE ROLE OF C-REACTIVE PROTEIN IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF VISUAL VASCULAR DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. Science and Innovation, 1(8), 114-121.
22. Jalalova, D., Raxmonov, X., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). SIGNIFICANCE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RETINOPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH AH AND WAYS OF ITS CORRECTION. Science and Innovation, 1(8), 101-113.
23. Jalalova, D., Axmedov, A., Kuryazov, A., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). COMBINED DENTAL AND EYE PATHOLOGY. Science and innovation, 1(8), 91-100.
24. Саттарова, Х. С., Жалалова, Д. З., & Бектурдиев, Ш. С. (2011). Причины слепоты и слабовидения при сахарном диабете. Академический журнал Западной Сибири, (6), 27-28.
25. Arunachalam, S. (2008). The science race continues in Asia. Current Science (00113891), 94(7).
26. Zukhriddinova, Z. D. (2022). Development of Classification Criteria for Neuroretinal Ischemia in Arterial Hypertension. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(3), 59-65.
27. Жалалова, Д. З., & Исмоилов, Ж. Ж. (2024). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ЭНДОТЕЛИНА-1 И Д-ДИМЕРОВ В КРОВИ И СЛЕЗНОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКОЙ АНГИОРЕТИНОПАТИЕЙ. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 3(3), 294-299.

28. Киселева, Т. Н. Ежов, М. В. Аджемян, Н. А. Танковский, В. Э. & Ильина, Н. В. (2016). Особенности регионарного глазного кровотока при артериальной гипертензии I-II степени и субклиническом атеросклерозе. Российский офтальмологический журнал, 9(3), 26-33.
29. Жалалова, Д. З. Кадирова, А. М. & Хамракулов, С. Б. (2021). Исходы герпетических кератоуевитов на фоне лечения препаратом «офтальмоферон» в зависимости от иммунного статуса пациентов. Междисциплинарный подход по заболеваниям органов головы и шеи, 103.
30. Дроздова, Е. А. & Хохлова, Д. Ю. (2015). Морфометрическая характеристика макулярной зоны у пациентов с окклюзией вен сетчатки по данным оптической когерентной томографии. Медицинский вестник Башкортостана, 10(2 (56)), 64-67.
31. Jalalova, D., Axmedov, A., Kuryazov, A., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). СОЧЕТАННАЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ И ГЛАЗНАЯ ПАТОЛОГИЯ. Science and innovation, 1(D8), 91-100.
32. Zhang, S., & Melander, S. (2014). Varicose veins: Diagnosis, management, and treatment. The Journal for Nurse Practitioners, 10(6), 417-424.
33. Жалалова, Д. З. & Бабаев, С. А. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ОЦЕНКИ УРОВНЯ ЭНДОТЕЛИНА-1 И Д-ДИМЕРОВ В СЛЕЗНОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИЕЙ. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 3(3), 300-307.
34. Zukhriddinova, Z. D. (2022). Development of Classification Criteria for Neuroretinal Ischemia in Arterial Hypertension. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(3), 59-65.